

Agroforestry in Finland

Stakeholders Policy challenges

- Full integration of agroforestry in other agricultural schemes
- Inventory of problems for each region and how was it solved
- Bureaucracy: management and processing usually at slow pace, administrative forms tedious.
- Permanent land use change
- Financial supports from state for too short a time period
- Legal framework non dynamic. Regulation non adapted to new productive and processing models.

Policy recommendations

- 1.- Development of working groups to fit funds to existing challenges, reduce bureaucracy at minimum and adapt the legal framework for agroforestry practices implementation in both forest and agricultural land uses.
- 2.- Develop advisory systems linked to global and local research.
- 3.- Establish a short, intermediate and long term strategy to ensure agroforestry transition based on knowledge and digitalization.
- 4.- Understanding agroforestry as a land management ecosystem services provider and a value chain promotion linked to the use of the territory.
- 5.- Better understanding between the different ministries (i.e. environment and agriculture).

STATE:	Finland		Silvopasture	2,42%	2,72%
Nut level:	1		Agrisilviculture	0,06%	0,04%
Eurostat code:	FI1		Agrosilvopasture	0,00%	0,00%
Area (km ²):	302.763		Kitchen gardens	0,21%	0,10%
Population	2018	2022	Holding type	2016	2023
Population	5.483.641	5.517.897	Natural person (ha)	1.852.870	1.740.930
Density (p km ⁻²)	18	18	Legal person (ha)	94.460	214.660
Cover data	2018	2022	Group holding and Common land unit (ha)	268.760	259.420
Forest	50,99%	31,67%	Natural person (holder)	43.130	35.580
Arable land	15,92%	7,06%	Legal person (holder)	1.430	1.980
Permanent crops	0,02%	0,02%	Group holding and Common land unit (holder)	4.740	4.370
Agroforestry	2,70%	2,86%	Regional Used Agricultural Area	2016	2023
Shrubland	4,30%	13,72%	Farm number	49.290	41.940
Grassland	8,66%	13,41%	Farm ha (UAA)	2.216.090	2.249.800
Agroforestry Practice Cover	2018	2022			

Animal populations (Thousand head)

	2018	2023
Live bovine animals	851	791
Dairy cows	262	235
Non dairy cows	57	61
Live swine, domestic species	1.041	963
Live sheep	-	-
Live goats	-	-

CROPS (Hectares)

	2016	2023
Utilised agricultural area	2.177.390	2.249.800
Cereals for the production of grain (including seed)	1.088.610	1.033.260
Common wheat and spelt	221.030	243.800
Durum wheat	-	-
Rye and winter cereal mixtures (maslin)	26.330	25.580
Barley	484.580	410.020
Oats and spring cereal mixtures	353.970	344.530
Grain maize and corn-cob-mix	-	-
Rice	-	-
Dry pulses and protein crops for the production of grain	46.620	70.450
Industrial crops	89.660	61.150
Cotton seed and fibre	-	-
Other oilseed crops n.e.c.	-	970
Fibre crops	-	430
Aromatic, medicinal and culinary plants	20.770	16.390

Plants harvested green from arable land	686.460	786.620
Green maize	-	-
Kitchen gardens	-	-

Rural Development Interventions promoting agroforestry

ENVCLIM(70) - Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments

Interventions	14
Forestry	14
Crop diversification including woody perennials	7
Crop rotation including woody perennials	14
Livestock including woody perennials	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil erosion	1
Woody perennials to add organic matter	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil chemical contamination	2
Animal welfare using woody perennials	6
Permanent Grasslands with woody perennials	1
Agroforestry on Permanent Crops	4
Interventions	14

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References

- Coverland data and Agroforestry practice cover: EUROSTAT LAND COVER/USE STATISTICS (LUCAS). <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/lucas/database/primary-data>
- Demographics and Farmland data: Eurostat, <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database>:
- Area by NUTS 3 region (demo_r_d3area) https://doi.org/10.2908/REG_AREA3
- Population on 1 January by age, sex and NUTS 2 region (demo_r_d2jan) https://doi.org/10.2908/DEMO_R_D2JAN
- Key farm variables area livestock (LSU) labour force and standard output (SO) by agricultural size of farm (JAA) legal status of holding and NUTS 2 regions (ef_kvaareg) https://doi.org/10.2908/EF_KVAAREG
- Farms and hectares by crops, utilised agricultural area, economic size of the farm and NUTS 2 region [ef_lus_allcrops_custom_21007488] https://doi.org/10.2908/EF_LUS_ALLCROPS
- Animal populations (December) by NUTS 2 regions [agr_r_animal] https://doi.org/10.2908/AGR_R_ANIMAL
- CAP Strategic Plans by country https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/cap-my-country/cap-strategic-plans_en#cap-strategic-plans-by-country